

Integration of Academic Knowledge and Active Citizenship: Service-Learning in Engineering Training

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Abstract:

Service Learning is a pedagogical methodology that combines academic knowledge with training aiming at the development of active citizenship (Diaz Fernandez, 2021). This approach is implemented through a carefully planned project in which students engage with the real needs of a community, contributing to its improvement. Service Learning is based on civic education, aligned with active learning and integrated with other approaches such as cooperative learning and project-based learning. Recent studies indicate that Service Learning offers considerable benefits to university students, promoting improvements in the quality of learning. Among the main benefits are the strengthening of leadership skills, the encouragement of attitudes of generosity, empathy and solidarity, increased self-esteem, the development of social skills, and the acquisition of significant learning (Narong, 2024). Service Learning is not just an isolated practical experience, but rather a way of integrating academic learning and social engagement, where students participate in activities that help develop essential skills and abilities for their professional future while responding to the needs of the community or society (Resch, 2023). This study aims to analyse how Service Learning can serve as a powerful educational tool, enabling students to develop essential technical and socio-emotional skills by engaging in real-world projects that integrate academic knowledge with professional and community challenges, ultimately promoting their growth as socially responsible and well-prepared citizens.

The projects developed by Mechanical Engineering and Electromechanical Engineering students at the Coimbra Institute of Engineering allowed the application of theoretical knowledge of Statistical Methods in practical situations, which not only improved the understanding of the concepts but also showed how these concepts can be used in real-world situations promoting sustainable solutions. The real data collected sometimes brings unexpected challenges, and students need to adapt, adjust methodologies and correct any flaws in the data or approaches adopted. Can students identify relevant problems and apply statistics to solve them effectively? Are students able to apply appropriate statistical techniques in the context of the proposed projects? Do students develop a broader view of their role as engineers in the social and community context? By reflecting on these questions, it is possible to identify both the challenges and

opportunities that arise during the process, as long as the development of students' potential technical and socio-emotional skills. When developing solutions, students can reflect on how their analyses can contribute to more sustainable practices in different areas. At the end of the project, students also had the opportunity to think about what they learned and how to apply their knowledge in the future.

Keywords: Service-learning; active methodology; cooperative learning; project-based learning; competencies; skills

Introduction

In recent years, the integration of Service-Learning (SL) methodologies into engineering education has gained significant momentum, driven by the dual objective of enhancing students' academic competencies while fostering civic responsibility and social engagement. Originating from the experiential learning paradigm (Kolb, 1984), SL is a pedagogical approach that combines formal academic instruction with community service, structured reflection, and reciprocal partnerships (Jacoby, 2015). When applied to STEM fields, and particularly to Mathematics and Statistics, SL has demonstrated its potential to bridge the gap between abstract theoretical concepts and the complex, nuanced challenges found in real-world social contexts (Hadlock, 2005; Queiruga-Dios et al., 2021). This methodological shift coincides with broader transformations in higher education, where there is increasing emphasis on developing transversal competencies, such as teamwork, ethical judgement, and communication, alongside technical proficiency (Niss & Højgaard, 2019; Alpers et al., 2013). Mathematics, traditionally taught as a self-contained discipline, is being reimagined as a fundamental discipline for interpreting, modelling, and transforming social realities (Zeidmane, 2012; Puzi et al., 2022). Within this context, SL offers a unique opportunity to reposition mathematical knowledge as a technical skill and as a civic instrument capable of generating social value (Bowman, 2011; McNatt, 2020). Despite its growing relevance, the incorporation of SL into mathematics and statistics education remains limited. A bibliometric review conducted by Narong & Hallinger (2024) revealed that less than 1% of SL projects indexed in major academic databases are explicitly related to mathematics education, highlighting a persistent underrepresentation of this field in SL research. Moreover, Queiruga-Dios et al. (2021, 2023) confirmed that within engineering curricula, SL projects involving mathematical modelling and data analysis are still relatively rare, though highly impactful when implemented. These findings align with recent efforts to promote SL practices through interdisciplinary collaborations between mathematics educators, engineering departments, and local community organisations (Frutos-Bernal et al., 2024; Dias Rasteiro, D. L., et al., 2024). The benefits of SL in mathematical contexts are multi-layered. First, it enables students to develop key mathematical competencies, such as reasoning, modelling, problem-solving, and statistical interpretation, in authentic contexts (Niss & Højgaard, 2019; Rasteiro et al., 2023). Second, it fosters reflective thinking by requiring students to evaluate how their academic expertise can contribute meaningfully to communities, particularly in contexts marked by inequality, vulnerability, or lack of access to data-driven decision-making. Third, SL

enhances motivation and engagement by allowing students to experience mathematics as a dynamic tool for diagnosing and acting upon real challenges (Muñoz-Medina et al., 2021).

Building on these principles, the present paper explores the integration of SL into the Statistical Methods curricular unit taught at the Coimbra Institute of Engineering (ISEC), Polytechnic University of Coimbra. During the 2024/2025 academic year, thirteen students engaged in this pedagogical experience, organised into three collaborative groups (two groups of four and one group of five). Guided by the SL framework, they were challenged to apply statistical concepts in response to real-world social and professional questions. The projects developed, analysing ethical consumption patterns, evaluating community service quality, and mapping financial literacy behaviours, serve as case studies for examining how mathematical competencies can be activated in contexts that also promote civic engagement and social reflection. Notably, one of the participating students had been diagnosed with Asperger syndrome, and his engagement in the group work and SL activities offers valuable insights into the inclusive potential of this pedagogical approach, which will be further discussed.

The structure of the paper is as follows: the present section provides a brief introduction to the use of Service-Learning methodology in educational contexts, highlighting its relevance for the development of mathematical and transversal competencies. In the following section the methodological framework, describing the participants involved in the study and detailing the SL procedures applied throughout the semester, is described. This is followed by the results and discussion section, where the main findings of the thirteen student-led projects are presented and critically analysed. The paper concludes with a synthesis of key outcomes and reflections, including considerations on inclusivity and directions for future research.

Methodology

This study was implemented within the framework of the curricular units Statistical Methods (from the Mechanical Engineering degree) and Linear Algebra (from the Electromechanical Engineering degree) at the Coimbra Institute of Engineering (ISEC), during the academic year 2024/2025. At the beginning of the semester, students were introduced to the concept of Service-Learning (SL) through a structured presentation prepared by the course coordinator, which outlined the pedagogical principles, societal relevance, and expected learning outcomes of the methodology. Following this session, students who voluntarily wished to engage in this approach registered via a Google Form. A total of 13 students applied: 7 from Statistical Methods and 6 from Linear Algebra.

In line with recognised SL frameworks (Rasteiro, D. M. L. D. et al, 2024; Jacoby, 2015; Queiruga-Dios et al., 2023), the experience followed seven structured phases: observation, preparation, action, reflection, data registration, evaluation, and recognition. During the observation phase, a collaborative brainstorming session allowed students to identify relevant social topics and possible contexts for intervention. The themes proposed reflected students' interests and were grounded in real-world challenges. All selected projects involved the design of a questionnaire, data collection in the field, and statistical data analysis. Regular meetings with the authors were held throughout the

semester to support survey development, validate research questions, and guide the application of analytical methods.

Figure 1 illustrates the interdisciplinary process conducted between Linear Algebra and Statistical Methods students. The flowchart summarises the sequence of activities, from problem identification to group analysis, presentation, and reflection. This visual representation reflects the cumulative and interconnected nature of the learning process.

Figure 1. Structured workflow of the interdisciplinary Service-Learning activity, combining statistical modelling and linear algebra to address real-world problems.

Students were organised into three working groups (two groups of four students and one of five), mixing participants from the two-degree programmes to foster interdisciplinary collaboration. Importantly, one student participating in the experience had a diagnosis of Asperger syndrome.

One of the students participating in this Service-Learning experience was diagnosed with Asperger syndrome, a condition within the autism spectrum characterised by difficulties in social communication, sensory sensitivity, and the need for structured environments. In traditional mathematical learning settings, students with Asperger syndrome may face challenges related to group dynamics, ambiguity in instructions, or limited flexibility in assessment formats (Baron-Cohen et al., 2009; Hedley et al., 2018). To address these needs, differentiated pedagogical strategies were adopted, including the clear definition of roles within the group, the use of asynchronous tools for reflection, and increased instructor mediation in moments of uncertainty. The structured and purpose-driven nature of SL, especially when tied to real societal needs, offered a more predictable and meaningful learning context. Inclusive support strategies were adopted, especially in managing group dynamics and promoting meaningful engagement in all SL phases. His successful participation added a valuable perspective on the potential of SL to support diverse learners. Moreover, authentic engagement and the possibility to contribute with analytical skills to a tangible community-oriented outcome promoted a sense of competence and inclusion for this student, suggesting that SL can be a powerful pedagogical strategy to support neurodivergent learners within Engineering Education.

The projects developed were as follows:

Group 1 investigated ethical consumption and sustainability in the fashion industry, analysing student behaviours regarding fast fashion platforms such as Shein and Temu. Using a structured questionnaire, they examined the influence of gender, price, and social media on purchase decisions and environmental awareness.

Group 2 partnered with the Angolan company Deanjamba to conduct a customer satisfaction and service effectiveness study. Their survey assessed perceived service quality, clarity of communication, responsiveness, and customer loyalty indicators. The project led to actionable recommendations to improve operations.

Group 3 explored financial literacy and investment behaviours among students at ISEC. Their data collection focused on investment habits, risk tolerance, financial planning, and educational needs. Statistical correlations were used to map relationships between behaviour and financial preparedness.

All groups used Microsoft Excel and/or IBM SPSS (version 27) for data analysis, supported by continuous authors' feedback. Deliverables included a written group report and an oral presentation of findings to peers. These were complemented by structured reflection exercises throughout the semester, allowing students to critically evaluate their experience and identify areas for personal and professional growth.

Assessment of student learning was conducted through a combination of formative and summative instruments. Formative assessment occurred during regular guidance meetings and feedback on interim results. Summatively, students completed a pre- and post-questionnaire designed to evaluate perceived competence development across areas such as problem-solving, teamwork, communication, civic engagement, and critical thinking. The results of these questionnaires are analysed in the following section.

From an ethical perspective, all student groups were instructed on good practices for data collection, including ensuring voluntary participation, anonymisation of responses, and transparency about the educational nature of the activity. Participants in all surveys were informed of these terms, and all data were processed following institutional guidelines for student-led research. It is important to state that the SL activities were aligned with the intended learning outcomes of the respective curricular units. In Statistical Methods, these included competencies in sampling, descriptive statistics, inferential techniques, and data interpretation. In Algebra, logical reasoning and the handling of data structures were reinforced through applied tasks. This constructive alignment ensured students developed content mastery and transversal skills within a coherent pedagogical framework.

Finally, students who did not opt into the SL track followed an alternative learning path based on more traditional problem-solving activities. This parallel structure ensured flexibility while maintaining equal opportunities for curriculum achievement.

Results and Discussion

The three Service-Learning (SL) projects developed by the student groups provided rich empirical data and insight into the transformative learning processes that occur when academic knowledge is meaningfully connected to societal concerns. Each project addressed a distinct theme, yet all shared common features: autonomous questionnaire design, purposeful data collection, and application of statistical analysis methods aligned with the learning outcomes of the Statistical Methods curricular unit. This section presents a synthesis of the main findings and discusses their implications for engineering education and the development of mathematical competencies.

3.1 Ethical Consumption and Sustainability Awareness

The first group focused on the topic of fast fashion, particularly the purchasing behaviours associated with online platforms such as Shein and Temu. The students explored correlations between socio-demographic variables (e.g., age, gender, income) and attitudes towards sustainability, price sensitivity, and social media influence. Their findings revealed a gender effect: female respondents were more likely to express concern about environmental impacts while simultaneously reporting higher purchase frequency from low-cost platforms. This duality led to a discussion of the attitude-behaviour gap, which students interpreted using statistical correlations and thematic clustering.

Pedagogically, the project enabled the development of competencies in survey design, data cleaning, cross-tabulation, and chi-square testing. More importantly, it prompted students to reflect critically on the ethical dimensions of consumption. This reflection, rarely triggered in traditional mathematical tasks, was later referenced by students in their post-questionnaires as one of the most "eye-opening" aspects of the learning experience.

3.2 Community-Oriented Data Analytics for Service Quality

The second group partnered with Dcanjamba, an Angolan company, which assisted students' online presentation, offering services in the tourism and business consultancy sector. Students designed a comprehensive questionnaire to evaluate customer satisfaction, perceived service quality, and competitive positioning. The final data set included over 100 valid responses and was analysed using descriptive statistics, cross-tabulations, and measures of central tendency. In their report, the group highlighted that perceived clarity of service conditions and response time were the most significant predictors of overall satisfaction. Results also indicated a strong likelihood of customer recommendation, although communication issues were noted in open-ended responses.

This project was particularly effective in demonstrating the value of data-driven decision-making in a real organisational context. Students engaged deeply with practical challenges such as designing unbiased response options, dealing with ambiguous qualitative data, and interpreting results for non-technical audiences. Their presentation to the company included actionable suggestions, demonstrating that SL can function not only as a learning method but also as a form of community consultancy grounded in rigorous analysis.

3.3 Financial Literacy and Investment Behaviour among University Students

The third project addressed an internal community challenge: the lack of financial planning and investment awareness among university students. The group conducted a detailed survey involving over 100 participants, focusing on areas such as risk perception, investment channels, saving habits, and planning behaviours. Through correlation analysis (e.g., Spearman's ρ), they observed a statistically significant relationship between financial planning and the presence of an emergency savings fund, as well as between risk tolerance and investment value.

The group concluded that although many students expressed interest in investing, a lack of structured knowledge and confidence hindered them from doing so. These findings support ongoing calls for the integration of financial education into engineering curricula, as advocated in recent European Commission recommendations. The SL process helped students articulate real statistical questions, draw valid conclusions from real data, and

present them with clarity to an academic audience, thereby reinforcing mathematical competencies while addressing a problem of social relevance.

3.4 Cross-Project Reflections and Competency Development

Across all three projects, students consistently reported growth in transversal competencies such as teamwork, communication, initiative, and social responsibility. The pre- and post-questionnaire included 21 items, adapted from Coverdell’s World Wise Schools rubric (Peace Corps, 1998), assessing dimensions such as teamwork, critical thinking, problem-solving, empathy, and the ability to connect theory and practice. A complete list of the items is provided in Table 1 (Annexe 1). From a mathematical point of view, students exercised statistical reasoning, modelling, and representation using tools like Excel and SPSS. An analysis of the pre- and post-questionnaire scores revealed perceived gains in a substantial number of competencies as may be observed in Figure 2. Specifically, improvements were noted in areas such as collaboration and teamwork (Q2), leadership skills (Q3), and civic responsibility (Q6), which are central to the social dimension of Service-Learning (SL). Additionally, students reported higher levels of engagement with the community (Q7), an increased sense of agency in effecting change (Q8), and a stronger ability to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world contexts (Q9, Q18). Gains were also observed in problem analysis and critical thinking (Q10), as well as in self-confidence (Q12) and conflict resolution (Q13), indicating growth in interpersonal and reflective skills. Further areas of perceived development included the assumption of personal responsibility (Q14), acquisition of practical workplace skills (Q15), experiential learning capacity (Q16), and empathy and sensitivity to others (Q20). While these changes were not statistically significant due to the small sample size, their breadth and alignment with the intended learning outcomes of the SL experience suggest a positive impact on both cognitive and socio-emotional dimensions of student development.

Figure 2. Average Likert scores (1-7) for selected competencies in the pre- and post-questionnaires.

While visual differences are observable, these results reflect the students' self-assessment of competencies before and after the Service-Learning experience. Further analysis is required to determine the statistical significance of perceived changes.

To complement the visual analysis of the pre- and post-questionnaire responses, paired statistical tests were conducted for the selected competencies (Q1, Q2, Q3, Q6, Q16, and Q18). Both paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were applied to assess whether the observed score variations were statistically significant. Results indicate that, although there were visible increases in mean scores for several items, particularly those related to teamwork, leadership, and learn from experience, none of the changes reached statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). This outcome is consistent with the relatively small sample size ($n = 10$ out of 13 students who participated in the study) and the moderate scale of change reported by students. Nonetheless, the directionality of the results, aligned with student reflections and group outputs, supports the pedagogical relevance of SL for fostering transversal competencies, even if these gains were not statistically confirmed within this sample. These gains tend to validate the role of SL in bridging the technical and human dimensions of engineering education. Particularly, the inclusive design of the activities also supported differentiated learning pathways: the student with Asperger syndrome reported benefiting from the structured phases, the clear goals, and the predictability of SL work, suggesting that this methodology may offer a more accessible environment for neurodivergent learners.

3.5 Interdisciplinary Collaboration with Linear Algebra Students

Aside from the primary SL projects, an interdisciplinary framework was established among students of the Linear Algebra (Electromechanical Engineering) and the Statistical Methods (Mechanical Engineering). Students in Linear Algebra were engaged in a voluntary and extracurricular activity centred on enabling data collection and organisation of mathematics for SL projects. Even though the Linear Algebra syllabus is not directly related to statistical data analysis, such as in the Statistical Methods course, these students participated enthusiastically in the interdisciplinary practice, which proved useful in the transversal skills reinforcement, like communication, initiative, and interpretation of data. All students received a grade from 0 to 4 depending on the quality of their contribution, the algebraic content of their statistical results, and the quality of their analysis. The median score was 3.04, and the first and third quartiles were 2.58 and 3.5. Figure 3 displays the grade distribution.

Figure 3. Grade distribution (0-4 scale) of students from Statistical Methods and Linear Algebra involved in the interdisciplinary Service-Learning activity

Conclusions:

This study explored the integration of Service-Learning (SL) into the teaching of Statistical Methods and Linear Algebra within engineering education, as part of a broader effort to link mathematical content with socially relevant challenges. Through three student-led projects, the initiative demonstrated that SL is not only effective in consolidating curricular content, such as survey design, data analysis, and statistical inference, but also in fostering critical transversal competencies, including teamwork, leadership, social awareness, and the ability to connect theory with practice.

An analysis of the pre- and post-questionnaire scores revealed perceived gains in a substantial number of competencies. While these changes were not statistically significant due to the small sample size, their breadth and alignment with the intended learning outcomes of the SL experience suggest a positive impact on both cognitive and socio-emotional dimensions of student development. These findings align with previous literature supporting the use of SL to enhance motivation and learning in STEM contexts (Jacoby, 2015; Queiruga-Dios et al., 2023) and reinforce the value of engaging students with real-world issues as a means of deepening both conceptual understanding and civic consciousness.

Beyond cognitive gains, this experience highlighted the inclusive potential of SL in diverse classroom settings. The successful engagement of a student with Asperger syndrome revealed that the structured, socially relevant, and purpose-driven nature of SL can provide an enabling environment for neurodiverse learners. This points to the need for further investigation into how active methodologies, particularly those involving community engagement, can support differentiated learning and foster a sense of belonging in engineering education.

The integration of Linear Algebra students from the Electromechanical Engineering course into the service-learning project, albeit voluntary and extracurricular, was an enriching complement. Collaboration with Statistical Methods students from the Mechanical Engineering course provided all students with an interdisciplinary environment in which mathematical reasoning, data analysis and teamwork were developed together. This experience validates the great potential in developing different programmatic contents through teamwork in problem-solving activities. The positive results suggest this complementary involvement can be pedagogically rewarding and academically enriching.

Finally, the projects conducted this year, focused on ethical consumption, service quality, and financial literacy, reflected students' ability to identify, formulate, and analyse problems of societal relevance using mathematical tools. They served not only as pedagogical experiments but also as authentic contributions to the community. Future work will focus on refining assessment tools, exploring long-term impacts on student learning trajectories, and expanding interdisciplinary SL opportunities across engineering curricula.

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Annexe 1:

Table 1. Competency Development Items Used in Pre- and Post-Questionnaire

Adapted from Coverdell's World Wise Schools rubric (Peace Corps, 1998)

Code	Item
Q1	Experience personal growth
Q2	Ability to work well with others
Q3	Improve my leadership skills
Q4	Improve my communication skills
Q5	Gain a greater understanding of cultural and racial differences
Q6	Improve my social responsibility and citizenship skills
Q7	Increase community involvement

Q8	Ability to influence the community
Q9	Apply information learned in the classroom to real-life scenarios
Q10	Enhance problem analysis and critical thinking
Q11	Apply problem-solving techniques
Q12	Build my self-confidence
Q13	Improve my conflict resolution skills
Q14	Take personal responsibility
Q15	Learn practical skills relevant to the workplace
Q16	Learn from experience
Q17	Develop organisational skills
Q18	Connect theory with practice
Q19	Establish meaningful interpersonal relationships
Q20	Develop empathy and sensitivity to others' situations
Q21	Demonstrate that I am someone who can be trusted

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